

A REVIEW :- SATELLITE PHOTOGRAMMETRY & ITS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The recent development and rapid evolution of modern sensors and new processing strategies of collected data have paved the way for innovations in photogrammetry. This Paper provides an overview of satellite photogrammetry and concentrates on earth observation satellites that operate in the optical spectrum. Which includes a comparison of high- and medium-resolution commercial imaging satellites. Photogrammetry is the art, science, and technology of obtaining reliable information about physical objects and the environment through processes of recording, measuring, and interpreting photographic images and patterns of recorded radiant electromagnetic energy and other phenomena

I. INTRODUCTION

Photogrammetry is nearly as old as photography itself. Since its development approximately 150 years ago, photogrammetry has moved from a purely analog, optical-mechanical technique to analytical methods based on computer-aided solution of mathematical algorithms and finally to digital or softcopy photogrammetry based on digital imagery and computer vision, which is devoid of any opto-mechanical hardware. Photogrammetry is primarily concerned with making precise measurements of three-dimensional objects and terrain features from two-dimensional photographs. Applications include the measuring of coordinates; the quantification of distances, heights, areas, and volumes; the preparation of topographic maps; and the generation of digital elevation models and orthophotographs.

Two general types of photogrammetry exist: aerial (with the camera in the air) and terrestrial (with the camera handheld or on a tripod). Terrestrial photogrammetry dealing with object distances up to ca. 200 m is also termed close-range photogrammetry. Small-format aerial photogrammetry in a way takes place between these two types, combining the aerial vantage point with close object distances and high image detail.

Common Applications of Satellite Photogrammetry.

The four most common mapping projects that utilize satellite imagery include:

- (1) Orthomosaics,
- (2) Planimetric Mapping,
- (3) classification Mapping, and
- (4) Topographic Mapping

Orthomosaics.

Most satellite imagery comes geo-referenced but not ortho rectified. Ortho rectification is a process that corrects inherent distortions in the optics and viewing geometry. The process incorporates a satellite orbital model, a digital elevation model (DEM) and optionally photo-identifiable ground control points (GCPs). Ortho rectification is the most reliable way to correctly georeference all points in an image.

- In addition to improving the absolute accuracy of the imagery, ortho rectification also improves the relative spatial match across adjacent scenes and strips. However, if the source scenes have different or opposite look angles, some spatial mismatch may be unavoidable, especially in high-relief areas.
- If an area of interest (AOI) comprises more than one scene/strip, the imagery also can be tonally balanced. Tonal balancing matches colors that otherwise would vary across adjacent scenes due to a variety of factors, including atmospheric conditions and vegetation seasonality across

multiple imagery acquisition dates. In cases of extreme seasonality differences, it may not be possible to create an entirely seamless tonal match.

- Typically, tonal balancing only is applied to land areas, not water, as the appearance of water features, especially saltwater, can vary greatly across multiple dates/scenes. If a visually pleasing or realistic picture is desired, water areas can be manually manipulated with software tools such as Photoshop, but image intelligence, such as shallow water depth, would be lost.
- To the extent possible, limiting the seasonality differences across strips helps improve tonal balancing. If an AOI comprises multiple scenes, some satellite operators will crop out part of the overlap area to reduce the file size. From an image processing perspective, however, especially where imagery needs to be cloud-patched, the overlap is desirable and should be available at no extra charge, as long as it's requested when the order is placed. Figure 1-1 and Figure 1-2 show how multiple overlapping scenes can be used to output a tonally balanced orthomosaic with cloud patching
- When creating orthomosaics, limiting the number of scenes facilitates processing, and, if applicable, helps reduce the total number of optimal Global Positioning System (GPS) GCPs. In the United States, public-domain products, such as imagery from the National Agriculture Imagery Program (NAIP), can be used as control to improve the ortho accuracy of imagery with lower native accuracy. Outside of the United States, if GPS GCPs aren't available, ideally the next-generation imaging sensors with higher native accuracy, such as GeoEye-1, WorldView-1 and WorldView-2, should be favored.

Fig.:1.1 Overlapping satellite image scenes with cloud
with

patching

Fig.:1.2 Tonally balanced orthomosaic Produced
cloud

cloud

Planimetric Mapping.

Vector extraction from satellite imagery allows roads, hydrology, building footprints and other planimetric features to be mapped cost effectively, or to update existing maps. The resulting accurate, up-to-date base data then are used to support the applications such as Internet mapping portals and handheld GPS device

- Unlike classification maps, which require multispectral imagery to emphasize the spectral properties of various features, feature extraction is based on spatial properties – the size and shape of objects – so pan imagery can be used. Color imagery, however, makes it easier to identify certain features such as water, paved vs. unpaved roads, etc.
- Despite advancements with machine learning and object-based image analysis, features such as roads, streams, and building footprints are still often captured via manual heads-up digitizing from orthomosaics. Computer-aided design (CAD) applications typically work best with 8-bit imagery, with a contrast stretch already applied to the imagery. Especially in AOIs of high relief or those comprising more than one scene,

imagery should be orthorectified prior to feature extraction. Figure 2.1 shows how satellite imagery can be used for vector extraction of roads, hydrology and other planimetric features

- Wavelet compressed file formats, such as ECW, MrSID and JPEG 2000, help facilitate file transfer across multiple production/quality assurance teams. Otherwise, it may help to tile GeoTiff imagery, as some CAD programs are limited in their ability to work with largraster files. Whenever possible, seasonality consideration should be given to AOIs, as leaf-off imagery yields better feature visibility.

Classification Mapping

Classification maps are one of the most common types of products created from satellite imagery and can map broad categories of land cover such as forest vs. agriculture or specific plant species. They also can map land use such as urban, industrial, residential, suburban and open space. These types of “clutter” maps are used in radio-frequency modeling for wireless networks, among other applications. Traditionally, classification work has been spectral pixel-based, so 11-bit, four-band imagery or better is used; newer object-based image analysis methodologies can yield superior results, especially with high-resolution imagery and image datasets that may only be available as three-band and/or 8-bit. Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2 demonstrate how multispectral and infrared imagery is useful for classification mapping projects such as vegetation mapping.

II. TOPOGRAPHIC MAPPING.

Fig: 2.1 Satellite imagery used for Vector Feature extraction of planimetric features.

Fig: 3.1 Multispectral & Infrared imagery
vegetation

Fig: 3.2 Classification map of

Cloud-free stereo imagery is required for topographic mapping from either aerial photogrammetry or satellite photogrammetry. In parts of the world where it is possible to obtain cloud-free optical high-resolution satellite imagery, this may be the preferred solution when producing Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) for applications with required resolutions down to 1-meter and where dense forests do not block stereo views of the bare-earth terrain.

Topographic mapping can also be performed using radar satellites such as TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X which operate in tandem to create a three-dimensional map of the world; but this technology is best suited for tropical areas where 10-meter DEM resolution is acceptable

III. CONCLUSION:

This paper has shown examples of satellite- and ground-based stereo analysis of clouds. Regarding satellites comprises all techniques concerned with making measurements of real-world objects and terrain features from images. These may be aerial as well as terrestrial images, and they may be taken by film cameras, digital cameras or electronic scanners on tripods, airborne or space borne platforms. Applications include the measuring of coordinates, quantification of distances, heights, areas and volumes, preparation of topographic maps, and generation of digital elevation models and orthophotographs. Understanding the geometry of a single photograph is the basis for all measurement techniques.

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